

Oxidation of L-cysteine by Fe^{III}-1,10-phenanthroline complex : A kinetic study

S. Panda^a, S. Acharya^b and P. Mohanty^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Utkal University, Vani Vihar, Bhubaneswar-751 004, Orissa, India

E-mail : sandhya_panda2002@yahoo.com

^bHydro- and Electro-Metallurgy Department, Regional Research Laboratory (CSIR), Bhubaneswar-751 013, Orissa, India

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Abstract : Electron transfer reaction of iron(III)-1,10-phenanthroline by L-cysteine has been studied spectrophotometrically over the range 1.1 ≤ pH ≤ 2.26, 25 ≤ t ≤ 40 °C, 0.1 ≤ l ≤ 0.2, 4.5 ≤ 10⁵ [Fe^{III}]_T ≤ 6.5, 1.5 ≤ 10³ [phen]_T ≤ 6.0 and 3.0 ≤ 10³ [H₃A⁺] ≤ 7.0 mol dm⁻³. The products of the reaction are Fe^{II} and cystine. The ΔH° and ΔS° values for the electron transfer reaction are (4.5 ± 1) kJ/mol and (-149 ± 3) JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹. The electron transfer reaction between the oxidant [Fe(phen)₂(OH)₂]³⁺ and the zwitterionic form of the amino acid follows the rate law : k_{obs} = K₂K₃ [Sub]_T [Hphen] (k₁ + k₂K₁[H⁺]/([H⁺] + K₁ [H⁺]² + K₂K₃ [Hphen]_e + K₁K₂K₃ [H⁺] [Hphen]).

Keywords : L-Cysteine, iron(III), cystine.

Oxidation of L-cysteine using oxidants such as hexacyanoferrate(III), μ-oxo-bis-[aquabis-(2,2'-bipyridine) ruthenium(III)], N-bromobenzenesulphonamide, 12-tungstocobaltate(III), substituted cobalt phthalocyanines, vanadium(V) oxodiperoxo complexes, manganese(III), ceric(IV) ion, hexachloroiridate(IV), chromium(VI), potassium ferrate(VI), oxygen and iron(III) complexes has been carried out by several workers¹. The products of the redox reaction from L-cysteine were mostly L-cystine. We now report the kinetics and mechanism of its oxidation using one electron oxidant, Fe^{III}-1,10-phenanthroline complex in acid perchlorate medium.

Experimental

L-Cysteine (B.D.H.), NaClO₄ (E. Merck), HClO₄ (B.D.H.), 1,10-phenanthroline (E. Merck), were of analytical grade. Iron(III) perchlorate solution was prepared by published method². The free acid present in iron(III) stock solution is determined by ion-exchange technique³. Double-distilled water was used for making solutions. Ionic strength was maintained by using NaClO₄.

A Systronics digital-335 pH meter was used for pH measurement and was standardized by using National Bureau of Standard buffer. The absorption spectra of Fe^{III}-1,10-phenanthroline (at pH = 1.53) and the mixture (L-cysteine + Fe^{III}-1,10-phenanthroline) at the same pH changes with time (Fig. 1).

Kinetic measurement : Kinetic measurements were carried out spectrophotometrically using CECIL (UK) CE 7200 UV-

Vis spectrophotometer fitted with CECIL CE 2024 thermo-electronic controller. The reaction progress was monitored at 510 nm, pseudo first order conditions were maintained throughout the runs by using a large (>50 folds) excess of L-cysteine. The rate constants k_{obs}, were obtained from the slope of ln (A_t - A_∞) vs t plots, A_t and A_∞ stands for the absorbances at time t and at equilibrium respectively. The reported data represented as an average of duplicate runs reproducible to within ±3%. The correlation coefficient of plot used to determine k_{obs} was found to be 0.99 in most of the cases.

Stoichiometry and products : The reaction stoichiometry of [Fe^{II}]/[cysteine] indicates the possible formation of the cystine.

Under the present experimental conditions [H⁺] = 2.95 × 10⁻² mol/dm³ the product is normally identified by HPLC as Cys-S-S-Cys. The oxidation product of L-cysteine analysis is carried out by HPLC and FTIR, and established exclusive as the cystine (eq. (1)).

Characterisation of product complex : A mixture of Fe^{III}-1,10-phenanthroline and L-cysteine in a molar proportion 1 : 1 : 1 was heated on a water bath and left overnight at room temperature, when the product complex separated out, it was purified by recrystallization.

IR spectra were taken in a Shimadzu FTIR 8000 spectrophotometer. Most of the peaks of L-cysteine in the oxidation products retain its identity. The appearance of

infrared frequencies of carboxylate proton at 367 and 1635 cm^{-1} in the product and at 1348 and 1647 in L-cysteine suggests that this group remains unaffected during oxidation. Similar is the case with NH_3 proton. The NH $\bar{\nu}_{\text{stretching}}$ appeared at 1288 and 1423 cm^{-1} in the product and at 1273 and 1429 cm^{-1} in L-cysteine. A peak appearing at 2526 cm^{-1} in L-cysteine corresponds to S-H $\bar{\nu}_{\text{stretching}}$ which is seen to be absent in the product. The infrared spectrum L-cystine was compared with that of the product. Most of the peaks of L-cystine and the product were identical. Hence the oxidation product was identified to be L-cystine, a dimer of L-cysteine.

Table 1. Effect of $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]$, $[\text{Cys}]$, $[\text{phen}]$, pH and ionic strength (I) on the pseudo first order rate constant k_{obs} at various temperature

$[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] \times 10^5$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[\text{Phen}] \times 10^3$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[\text{L-Cys}] \times 10^3$ (mol dm^{-3})	pH	I (mol dm^{-3})	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4$ (s^{-1})	Temp. $^{\circ}\text{C}$	k_2 ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1} \text{dm}^3$)
4.5	6.0	3.0	1.53	0.1	3.21	25	0.102 ± 0.004
4.5	6.0	4.0	1.53	0.1	3.89	25	
4.5	6.0	5.0	1.53	0.1	5.15	25	
4.5	6.0	6.0	1.53	0.1	6.04	25	
4.5	6.0	7.0	1.53	0.1	7.05	25	
4.5	6.0	3.0	1.53	0.1	7.6	30	
4.5	6.0	4.0	1.53	0.1	9.51	30	
4.5	6.0	5.0	1.53	0.1	11.9	30	
4.5	6.0	6.0	1.53	0.1	13.7	30	
4.5	6.0	7.0	1.53	0.1	16	30	
4.5	6.0	3.0	1.53	0.1	8.91	35	0.3 ± 0.013
4.5	6.0	4.0	1.53	0.1	11.4	35	
4.5	6.0	5.0	1.53	0.1	14.3	35	
4.5	6.0	6.0	1.53	0.1	15.8	35	
4.5	6.0	7.0	1.53	0.1	19	35	
4.5	6.0	3.0	1.53	0.1	17	40	
4.5	6.0	4.0	1.53	0.1	22.44	40	
4.5	6.0	5.0	1.53	0.1	27.17	40	
4.5	6.0	6.0	1.53	0.1	29.41	40	
4.5	6.0	7.0	1.53	0.1	34.01	40	
4.5	6.0	3.0	2.26	0.1	4.57	25	0.53 ± 0.036
4.5	6.0	3.0	1.75	0.1	3.28	25	
4.5	6.0	3.0	1.45	0.1	2.43	25	
4.5	6.0	3.0	1.3	0.1	2.40	25	
4.5	6.0	3.0	1.1	0.1	1.96	25	
4.5	6.0	3.0	1.53	0.15	4.98	25	
4.5	6.0	3.0	1.53	0.18	4.89	25	
4.5	6.0	3.0	1.53	0.2	4.44	25	
5.5	6.0	3.0	1.53	0.1	4.32	25	
6.0	6.0	3.0	1.53	0.1	4.26	25	
6.5	6.0	3.0	1.53	0.1	4.19	25	
4.5	1.5	3.0	1.53	0.1	5.48	30	
4.5	2.5	3.0	1.53	0.1	7.06	30	
4.5	3.0	3.0	1.53	0.1	9.28	30	
4.5	4.0	3.0	1.53	0.1	12.9	30	
4.5	1.5	3.0	1.53	0.1	13.1	35	
4.5	2.5	3.0	1.53	0.1	24.1	35	
4.5	3.0	3.0	1.53	0.1	35.5	35	
4.5	4.0	3.0	1.53	0.1	56.7	35	

$$\Delta H^{\ddagger} = (4.5 \pm 1) \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$$

$$\Delta S^{\ddagger} = (-149 \pm 3) \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$$

Fig. 1. Repetitive spectral scans for the reaction of Fe^{III} with L-cysteine mixture. $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} = 4.5 \times 10^{-5}$, $[\text{L-cysteine}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{phen}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 1.53$, $\text{temp} = 34^{\circ}\text{C}$: (a) Fe^{III} only, (b) mixture after 10 min, (c)-(g) after 20, 30, 45, 60, 90 min interval respectively.

Results and discussion

Effect of variation of iron(III), cysteine, phenanthroline, ionic concentration (I), pH and temperature on the rate constants of oxidation has been given in Table 1. Only one of above factors was varied at a time keeping all other factors same. The rate of oxidation is first order dependent on the concentrations of iron(III), H^3A^+ , phenanthroline. Based on these observations, the mechanism of the reactions can be presented as :

Mechanism :

Scheme 1

The rate law for the redox reaction can be derived in the following manner.

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 + [C_1][\text{Sub}]_e + k_2[C_1][\text{HSub}]_e \quad (9)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = K_2K_3 [\text{Sub}]_T[\text{Hphen}] (k_1 + k_2K_1[\text{H}^+]) / ([\text{H}^+] + K_1[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_2K_3[\text{Hphen}]_e + K_1K_2K_3[\text{H}^+][\text{Hphen}]) \quad (10)$$

Conclusion :

L-Cysteine a sulphur containing amino acid has three coordination sites, oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur. The oxidation product of the amino acid was L-cystine. The rate of reaction decreases with $[\text{H}^+]$ indicating the conjugate base of the amino acid is more reactive than the amino acid. Low value of ΔS^\ddagger is in support of an ordered transition state for the electron transfer reaction.

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